

THE FORT THAT SPEAKS FROM THE PAST

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“National history should be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. We need to teach our youth to draw conclusions from history, equip them with historical knowledge and historical thinking.”

Shavkat Mirziyoyev

It is known from history that since ancient times the land of Khorezm was located in the area surrounded by deserts and agriculture, which was the main source of livelihood, was based on artificial irrigation. These irrigation networks are one of the oldest irrigation networks in the history of the world, providing the entire region with water, which is the source of life. Naturally, such networks served not only to supply water to lands far from the river, but also to the development of urban planning culture, which began to develop slowly in its surroundings. One of the ancient fortresses of Khorezm that appeared in this direction is "Kardaronxos" or as we know it, "Qal'ajiq qal'a".

In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to ensure the rapid development of domestic tourism" dated 07.02.2018 No. PQ-3514, "Qal'ajiq qal'a" was included in the program for the development of domestic and foreign tourism in remote areas. After the implementation of this decision, the number of tourists coming to "Qal'ajiq qal'a" is increasing day by day. In this seasonal place, tourists from not only our country, from the neighboring country of Turkmenistan, but also from foreign countries are attracted by the conditions here, the teahouses reminiscent of our

past, and the 4-season vacation houses built in a modern style, the presence of camels and horses for taking pictures, a unique small Tourists who have enjoyed the bazaar, national dishes, various fruits, mouth-watering melons, enjoy the smell of saxophone growing in the sand here, nature and animal world, intend to come here again for treatment and pleasure.

During the day, the saxes and grasses growing green in the yellow-yellow sand dunes add to the beauty of the "Qal'ajiq qal'a" and in the evening, the reflection of the moon and stars falls on the blue water of the lake in front of the castle, and it seems as if there is a sky instead of ashes.

Also, a film called "Anchor of Khiva" is being shot here by the filmmakers of Uzbekistan, Turkey and India about our Great Grandfather Pahlovon Mahmud. In particular, those who said that on the day of the signing of contracts on the shooting of historical films by other foreign countries

In addition to increasing the economic, social and political power of Uzbekistan, we can understand the national identity and see our country among the highly developed countries of the world only by thoroughly studying the history and heritage of our ancestors.

For this purpose, since the first years of independence in our republic, great attention has been paid to the deeper study of our history.

In particular, the importance of archeology in studying the culture of urban planning in Khorezm is incomparable.

Studying the history of the ancient and medieval cities of South Khorezm and its material culture, as well as the topographical structure, is one of the problems that have not been fully investigated scientifically. Within this problem, the main attention can be paid to the types of cities of average size in terms of size.

"Qal'ajiq qal'a", located on the left bank of the Amudarya in the territory of the ancient Khorezm state, belongs to this type of cities. The study of this city is of historical importance in many ways, firstly, it can help to study the history of urban planning culture in Khorezm, secondly, to solve the problems of the ancient statehood of Khorezm, and thirdly, it can help to develop tourism, which is one of the most relevant policies of our country today. And finally, the presence of healing lake waters and sand allows to turn the monument "Qal'ajiq qal'a" into one of the centers of archeo-ecotourism.

If we talk about the written sources about the monument "Qal'ajiq qal'a", this monument is located in Bogot District, 25 km from Hazorasp city and 21 km west of the district center. The fortress has an irregular rectangular shape, the length of the northern wall is 184 m, the southern wall is 211 m, the western wall is 72 m, and the eastern wall is 114 m. The total area is 6 hectares. Dated to the IV century BC.

The first information about "Qal'ajiq qal'a" is mostly found in Arab-Persian sources of the IX-XII centuries. Because in these centuries a high level of economic and cultural development is observed in all Eastern regions. At the same time, this information about our topic is important because the authors of these sources have only mentioned the events that they saw and witnessed.

"Qal'ajiq qal'a" is mentioned in medieval sources under different names. In the work "Hudud al-Olam" by an unknown author and written in Persian, it is mentioned in the works of authors such as Kardnaskhaz, al-Istakhri and al-Maqdisi as Kardarankhosh and Kardarankhos, and in the works of Khorezm historians such as Abulhazi, Munis and Ogahi with the names Kardan khast or Gardan khast. done. But these sources have different opinions about Kardaranchos and its size. For example, "Hudud al-Olam" records that the city was a small town, but was surrounded by a rich agricultural oasis and many villages, while in al-Istakhri it is now described as a large fortress with a strong defense system like Hazorasp.

According to Maqdisi, it was a strong fortification with large wooden gates and a moat, and a trade center.

Although there are different opinions about the meaning of the word "Qal'ajiq", most scholars believe that it means "small fortress".

The folk name of "Qal'ajiq qal'a" is "Davudqal'a", and this name is related to the legend of "Davudpir", a blacksmith's forge.

Currently, in order to develop tourism, study our history and preserve the historical monuments that have come down to us and deliver them to the next generation, renovation works are being carried out, as well as the laying of asphalt pavements on the roads to get there.

These will certainly serve to increase the spirituality of our youth, to introduce our country to the world, to develop international tourism, to raise our national

values, to increase the love and loyalty of our people to the motherland, and to realize our identity.

The article was written using information from the book "Qal'ajiq-qal'a" by Gudrat Masharipov and Kuvondik Rozmetov.